

display subnormal magnetic moment values at room temperature. The magnetic moment values of dihalo complexes (1.77–1.91 BM) indicate that they are magnetically dilute³⁻⁶. In case of inner bischelates CuL_2 , the subnormal magnetic moment values of the complexes can be attributed to spin-spin interaction by the overlap of d_{z^2} or $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbitals between two Cu(II) atoms and this interaction in case of $\text{Cu}(\text{BT})_2$ is so strong that paramagnetism associated with cupric ion is completely quenched⁴⁻⁶. In case of bulky ligand molecules like MBTH and CBTH this interaction is rather less and therefore partial quenching is observed in their inner complexes⁶.

Inner bischelates of Ni(II) also display anomalous magnetic moment values at room temperature ($\mu_{eff} = 1.51 - 2.69$ BM) attributable to the presence of varying proportion of 6-coordinated distorted octahedral species along with planar nickel(II) species^{7,9}. The magnetic moment values of Co(II) complexes ($\mu_{eff} = 2.01 - 2.76$ BM) are similar to square planar or spin-paired octahedral complexes⁹. The magnetic moment values of $\text{Ni}(\text{LH})_2\text{Cl}_2$ [LH=BTH or MBTH] fall between 2.89 BM and 3.38 BM which are in the range of octahedral nickel(II) complexes^{10,11}.

The reflectance spectra of CoL_2 [LH=BTH or MBTH] display two weak bands or shoulders at 16130–18520 cm^{-1} and 21740–22570 cm^{-1} assignable to d-d transitions⁹. The dihalo as well as neutral copper(II) complexes CuL_2 display a broad and asymmetric band in the region 12500–13500 cm^{-1} attributable to the combination of ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{A}_{1g} + {}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_{2g}$ transitions in distorted octahedral field¹²⁻¹⁴. The strong absorption at 24500–25320 cm^{-1} in $\text{Cu}(\text{BT})_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{LH})\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ can be attributed to charge transfer plus some contribution of ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$ transition. Dihalonickel(II) complexes display three weak or medium bands at 11350–11430, ~15750 and 24390–26520 cm^{-1} assignable to transitions¹⁵ ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{2g}(\text{F})$, $\rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F})$ and $\rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ respectively. The neutral bischelate $\text{Ni}(\text{BT})_2$ displays d-d transitions at 10750, 15380 and 24040 cm^{-1} as a shoulder or a very weak band. In case of the orange red complex $\text{Ni}(\text{MBT})_2$ the d-d transitions are observed at 10530, 20000, 22570 and 24570 cm^{-1} . The band at 22570 cm^{-1} can be attributed to ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{B}_{1g}$ transition from the planar nickel(II) species in the complex¹⁶.

The ligands display a number of bands around 3μ region due to $\nu(\text{NH}_2)$, $\nu(\text{NH})$, $\nu(\text{CH}_2)$ and phenyl ring $\nu(\text{C-H})$ stretching vibrations (BTH, 3260m, 3170m, 3058m, 2998, 2884 and in CBTH at 3300m, 3210m, 3080m, 3015m and 2900w cm^{-1}). In some complexes, these bands between 3300–3000 cm^{-1} are affected appreciably in intensity and position but from this it is difficult to suggest the nature of bonding and deprotonation of the ligands.

The $\nu(\text{C=O})$ vibration of the free ligands (in BTH, 1676; CBTH, 1660 cm^{-1}) is shifted to higher wave number in their complexes by 10–40 cm^{-1} indicating that the oxo-oxygen is not involved in coordination.

The $\delta(\text{NH}_2)$ and $\beta(\text{NH}_2)$ of free ligands (BTH, 1600 and 1230 cm^{-1} , CBTH, 1584 and 1215 cm^{-1}) are shifted to higher frequencies in their complexes

which suggests that NH_2 nitrogen is involved in coordination with metal atoms¹⁷.

The thioamide bands (I to III)^{18,19} of the ligands (BTH, 1550vs, 1319m, 1065m cm^{-1} and of CBTH at 1540s, 1315m and 1070m cm^{-1}) are shifted to higher frequencies in complexes, indicative of bonding from thioxo sulphur of the ligand molecules. The thioamide band IV of BTH located at 888 cm^{-1} and of CBTH at 890 cm^{-1} is shifted to lower frequency by 155–200 cm^{-1} in neutral chelates indicating the bonding of thioxo sulphur by deprotonation of thiol form of the ligands. It is thus inferred that amino nitrogen and thioxo sulphur are the bonding sites of the ligand molecules in almost all the complexes.

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Alkali Metal Complexes: Adducts of Alkali Metal Salts of 1-Nitroso-2-Naphthol with Thiourea

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Manuscript received 30 May 1981, accepted 22 July 1981

TO unravel the mechanism of active transportation and storage of alkali metals from soil to plants in aqueous media, we have prepared some adducts of alkali metals with sulphur containing ligand in aqueous medium. Earlier Banerjee *et al.*^{1,2} prepared a number of similar adducts with oxygen and nitrogen containing ligands.

NOTES

In the present work adducts of alkali metal salts of 1-nitroso-2-naphthol with thiourea have been synthesised and their structures investigated with particular reference to their coordination sites.

Results and Discussion

Our usual method of synthesis was to take a saturated solution of thiourea in distilled water and to add alkali metal salts of 1-nitroso-2-naphthol to it. The mixture was stirred well at room temperature for two hrs. The solution was concentrated at low temperature when reddish brown solid separated out.

Analytical data showed that one molecule of alkali metal salt of ML (where M=Li, Na or K and L=deprotonated 1-nitroso-2-naphthol) combined with two molecules of thiourea (tu) and the general formula of the adducts have been established as ML.2tu.

The compounds are thermally stable and show no change in stoichiometry or physical properties even after one year. They are soluble in common organic solvents and absorb water when exposed to moisture. The

The formation of S-M bonds is expected to increase the contribution of highly polar structure of the thiourea molecule, resulting in a greater double bond character for the nitrogen to carbon bond and an increased single bond character for the carbon to sulphur bond.

The assignment of the absorption bands observed for the alkali metal-thiourea adducts are as follows : The bands in the 3400-3100 cm^{-1} region are undoubtedly assigned to the N-H stretching vibrations. These bands are sharper in the adducts pointing out that hydrogen bonding is not present in them. The strong bands observed at 1618 cm^{-1} correspond to the bands of thiourea of almost the same frequency and can be attributed to the NH_2 bending vibrations. The nature of the 1471 cm^{-1} band in thiourea is changed in the adducts. This C=S stretching vibration is split into two probably due to metal-sulphur bond² formation. The strong band at 1086 cm^{-1} of thiourea is weakened on adduct formation. This can be explained by considerable change in the nature of C=S bond on attachment of thiourea through sulphur atom³. The contribution of the C=S vibration at 1086 cm^{-1} in the adducts is decreased and the intensity of the band

TABLE 1

Compound	Colour	Transition/decomp. temp. (°C)	Found (%)				Calculated (%)				
			C	H	N	M	C	H	N	M	
tu	White	180 m									
LiIN2N.2tu	Reddish brown	140 d	43.74	4.14	20.80		43.50	4.22	21.14		
NaIN2N.2tu	Reddish brown	135 d	40.85	4.25	20.22	6.50	41.49	4.03	20.17	6.62	
KIN2N.2tu	Reddish brown	160 d	39.18	3.62	19.64	10.68	39.39	3.83	19.28	10.75	

TABLE 2—INFRARED ABSORPTION BANDS OF THIOUREA COMPLEXES OF ALKALI METAL SALTS OF 1-NITROSO-2-NAPHTHOL (cm^{-1})

tu	LiIN2N.2tu	NaIN2N.2tu	KIN2N.2tu
1618	1616	1618	1625
1471			
1412	1412	1418	1422
		1410	1405
1081	1086	1087	1510
	765		
730	745	732	745
	720	725 sh	715
	265	268	270

analysis and physical properties of the complexes are given in Table 1.

The infrared spectra of the complexes have been recorded from 4000-200 cm^{-1} in Nujol mulls (CsI disc). The selected absorption bands are given in Table 2.

The high frequency N-H absorption bands in the spectrum of thiourea were not shifted to lower frequencies on the formation of alkali metal-thiourea adducts. This indicates that nitrogen-metal bonds are not present and, therefore, the bonding in these adducts may be through sulphur.

reduced. The 730 cm^{-1} band of thiourea also shows a minor splitting but not appreciable change in frequency, particularly in the case of sodium-thiourea adduct. This is reasonable because the bondings are comparatively weak. The band at 265, 268 and 270 cm^{-1} in lithium, sodium and potassium adducts respectively shows the presence of M-S bond^{4,5} in them.

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for awarding a Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (M.K.G.).

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